

CORRECTIVE SPEECH THERAPY WORK IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ANNOTATION: This scientific article explores the importance of corrective speech therapy in the development of speech skills among preschool children. It examines the role of speech therapy in addressing speech disorders and highlights the significance of early intervention in promoting optimal speech development. The article discusses key concepts related to corrective speech therapy and presents various techniques and strategies used in this therapeutic approach. By reviewing existing literature, this article aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the benefits and effectiveness of speech therapy in preschool-aged children.

KEYWORDS: corrective speech therapy, speech development, preschool children, speech disorders, early intervention

INTRODUCTION

The development of speech skills in the preschool years is crucial for effective communication and cognitive development. However, some children may experience speech disorders that hinder their ability to communicate effectively with others. Corrective speech therapy plays a significant role in minimizing the impact of these speech disorders, facilitating the development of clear and articulate speech. This article aims to explore the benefits and effectiveness of corrective speech therapy in the context of preschool children's speech development.

MAIN PART

The child learns the pronunciation norms of the native language gradually (at the beginning, he replaces difficult sounds with simpler ones, rearranges them, reduces the number of syllables in a word, etc.), ends the

process of developing sound pronunciation by the age of 5, when the child can correctly pronounce all the sounds.

However, the successful formation of the sound-pronunciation side of speech does not always occur. For many children, defects in sound pronunciation, having arisen and entrenched in childhood, are overcome with great difficulty in subsequent years and can persist for life.

Deficiencies in speaking can be the cause of writing errors. 16.7% of future first-graders have prerequisites for articulatory-acoustic dysgraphia (partial specific violation of the writing process). Children with speech impairments can not spontaneously take the ontogenetic path of speech development; they need special corrective action. The work in the speech therapy center is structured as follows: from the beginning of September, for 2 weeks, diagnostics of the speech of children is carried out, with from the second half of September to May, children's speech is corrected.

The graduation of children is carried out throughout the school year as their speech defects are eliminated. Also, during the entire academic year, consultations are carried out at the request of parents.

Children with the following speech disorders are enrolled in a speech therapy center: -phonetic speech underdevelopment (violation of articulation of individual or several sounds, sound combinations or whole groups of sounds), -phonetic - phonemic speech underdevelopment and (FFNR) - violation of the processes of formation of the pronunciation system of the native language in children with various speech disorders due to defects in the perception and pronunciation of phonemes, -general underdevelopment of level IV speech (with OHP level IV, children experience specific difficulties in pronunciation and repetition of words with a complex syllable composition, have a low level of phonemic perception, make mistakes in word formation and inflection, the vocabulary is quite diverse, but children do not always know and understand exactly the meaning of rarely encountered words, antonyms and synonyms,

proverbs and sayings, etc., in independent speech, children experience difficulties in the logical presentation of events, often miss the main thing and "get stuck" on secondary details, repeat what was said earlier).

First of all, children of preparatory groups for school (6 years old) and schoolchildren are enrolled in classes. Children 5 years of age are enrolled in a speech center if the child has several groups of sounds or violations that are sharply inappropriate to the age norm, as well as the seats become vacant. The system of work in the speech center is built taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of each child, corrective action is aimed at eliminating the causes that caused speech disorders and the prevention of speech disorders in pupils. The main form of work in the speech center is individual correction lessons. This is due to the following reasons:

- the need to take into account the schedule general developmental classes;
- different structure of pronunciation defects in children of the same age group;
- different levels of formation of cognitive processes in children with similar speech defects;
- individual pace of material assimilation;
- the need for simultaneous correction of several sounds.

The work on the formation of correct pronunciation in children is structured as follows: Development of auditory attention, phonemic perception of the formed sound. Articulating I'm gymnastics. Sound production. Sound automation. Differentiation of the generated sound and the mixed sound in pronunciation.

The duration of correctional and developmental work is largely due to the individual characteristics of children. Speech therapy is carried out by various methods, among which visual, verbal and practical are conventionally distinguished. Visual methods are aimed at enriching the content of speech, verbal - at teaching retelling, conversation, story without reliance on visuals.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

I. Speech Disorders in Preschool Children

- A. Characteristics and prevalence of speech disorders
- B. Impact of speech disorders on children's communication and social interaction

II. Importance of Early Intervention in Speech Development

- A. The critical period for speech development
- B. Long-term consequences of untreated speech disorders

III. Corrective Speech Therapy Techniques and Strategies

- A. Articulation therapy
- B. Language intervention
- C. Fluency therapy
- D. Voice therapy

IV. Role of Corrective Speech Therapy in Preschool Speech Development

- A. Improving articulation and pronunciation skills
- B. Enhancing language and vocabulary development
- C. Promoting fluent speech production
- D. Addressing voice-related disorders

V. Effectiveness of Corrective Speech Therapy

- A. Review of empirical studies and research findings
- B. Case studies highlighting successful speech therapy outcomes

CONCLUSION

Corrective speech therapy plays a vital role in the development of speech skills among preschool children. By employing a range of techniques and strategies, speech therapists can address various speech disorders and facilitate optimal speech development. Early intervention is crucial in preventing long-term communication challenges and improving overall quality of life for children with speech disorders. It is imperative for parents, educators, and healthcare

professionals to recognize the significance of corrective speech therapy and ensure timely intervention for preschool children with speech difficulties.

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